

The Role of Workplace Passion on Job Satisfaction: Person-Organization Fit as A Mediating Variable

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the relationship between work passion and job satisfaction, with a particular focus on the mediating role of person–organization fit. Work passion, especially harmonious passion, has been identified as a key psychological factor that fosters positive work-related outcomes such as commitment, creativity, and well-being. However, growing empirical evidence suggests that the influence of work passion on job satisfaction may not be linear or unconditional; rather, it is shaped by contextual factors such as organizational value congruence. Person–organization fit, defined as the alignment between an employee’s personal values and the organizational culture, is proposed as a central mediator that facilitates the effective transformation of passion into satisfaction.

To test the proposed model, a quantitative research approach was adopted. Data were collected through a structured survey administered to a purposive sample of 224 employees working in government-owned banks. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to analyze the relationships among the variables. The findings reveal that work passion significantly predicts job satisfaction, and this relationship is fully mediated by person–organization fit. Specifically, employees who perceive a strong alignment between their values and those of their organization experience higher levels of satisfaction, particularly when their work is driven by intrinsic passion. The study contributes to the growing field of positive organizational behavior by providing empirical support for the mediating role of person–organization fit in the passion–satisfaction link. It also offers practical implications for managers in the banking sector, emphasizing the need to create supportive environments that cultivate both personal passion and cultural alignment to enhance employee satisfaction and organizational effectiveness.

KEYWORDS: Work Passion, Job Satisfaction, Person–Organization Fit, Harmonious Passion, Public Sector Banking

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
2 June 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmir.com>

INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is a pivotal concept in the field of management and individual behavior within organizations, given its direct impact on job stability, organizational performance, and employee psychological well-being (Daneshmandi et al., 2023; Bhatia & Williams, 2023). Recent studies have examined the psychological factors underlying this satisfaction, most notably passion for work, as it is an intrinsic motivator that enhances commitment, stimulates engagement, and brings meaning to job tasks (Vallerand et al., 2023). Consensual passion, specifically, refers to an individual's flexible and healthy engagement with their work, which contributes to increased satisfaction and psychological balance (Forest et al., 2022).

However, the relationship between passion and job satisfaction cannot always be directly explained, as the literature indicates the presence of mediating factors that serve as the link that enables passion to achieve its full impact (Sulea et al., 2023; Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2023). The psychological climate within organizations plays a decisive role in shaping employee attitudes and outcomes. Prior organizational studies have emphasized the importance of supportive work environments in fostering positive employee experiences and sustainable performance (Al-Hassani, 2025a).

Among these factors, person-organization fit stands out as a mediating variable capable of explaining how intrinsic motivations translate into tangible organizational outcomes (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005). When employees feel that there is alignment between their values and the organization's culture, they feel more satisfied, even in the face of work-related stress, because the organizational

context provides an environment that nurtures and activates passion (Kaur & Kang, 2021). In light of the rapid transformations witnessed in the contemporary work environment and the increasing challenges associated with technology, competitiveness, and psychological pressures, interest has grown in the positive psychological variables that enhance employees' quality of life and support sustainable organizational performance (Luthans et al., 2007). Contemporary organizations, especially in dynamic sectors, are increasingly required to adapt to technological and environmental shifts. Recent research highlights how responsiveness to these shifts contributes to greater organizational adaptability and individual alignment (Al-Hassani & Ghoneim, 2025). Among these variables, the concept of work passion has emerged as a key element for understanding positive job behaviors and an important approach to enhancing individual performance, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction (Vallerand et al., 2023). Passion at work is defined as an individual's emotional and cognitive engagement with their professional activity, such that it becomes part of their identity without causing conflict with other areas of life, particularly in the case of "compatible passion" (Forest et al., 2022). Employee perceptions are not formed in isolation; they are deeply influenced by relational and contextual factors within the organization. Prior findings confirm that interpersonal quality within the workplace contributes significantly to employees' psychological engagement and alignment with organizational values (Al-Hassani, 2024).

The literature shows that passionate employees have high levels of intrinsic motivation and voluntarily invest their efforts in performing their tasks, generating a deep sense of satisfaction and psychological stability (Vallerand et al., 2023). However, this positive effect of passion is not always directly realized. Recent studies confirm that a supportive and compatible organizational environment is a necessary condition for transforming passion into tangible positive outcomes (Zhang et al., 2025). Conversely, unsupportive or toxic workplace climates have been shown to erode positive psychological states, reducing motivation and organizational commitment. Such environments hinder the transformation of positive attitudes into tangible outcomes (Al-Hassani, 2025b). Here, person-organization fit (P-O-F) emerges as a mediating variable that can explain how and why passion at work leads to job satisfaction (Chen et al., 2016).

P-O-F fit reflects the degree of alignment between an employee's values, beliefs, and goals, on the one hand, and the organization's culture and orientations (Cable & DeRue, 2002), on the other. This fit enhances employees' sense of belonging and acceptance, creating a psychological and social environment that contributes to motivation, reducing stress, and achieving balance between self and organization (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005; Kristof-Brown & Schneider, 2023). Studies have shown that employees who feel a fit with their organizations exhibit higher levels of satisfaction, even when the nature of the tasks is stressful or changing, because their perception of value congruence provides them with a sense of meaning and empowerment (Kaur & Kang, 2021).

From this perspective, the fit between the individual and the organization is a crucial explanatory mechanism in the relationship between passion and satisfaction. It is the mediator that translates the positive emotions resulting from passion into positive job outcomes, such as satisfaction and commitment. In the absence of this fit, passion can become a source of psychological stress, especially if the individual feels the organization does not reflect their values or appreciate their efforts. Therefore, examining this mediating role represents a qualitative addition to models of organizational behavior and helps build a balanced work environment that motivates employees and supports their psychological and professional health. Based on the above, this study aims to explore the relationship between work passion and job satisfaction, and to test the mediating role played by the fit between the individual and the organization. The results of this study are expected to contribute to developing a theoretical understanding of the psychological factors influencing satisfaction, in addition to providing practical recommendations for human resource management to enable it to attract passionate employees and enhance their alignment with the organizational culture, thus supporting sustainable performance and employee loyalty.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. Passion in the Workplace

Passion is an important psychological variable that plays a crucial role in achieving high levels of performance, job satisfaction, and creativity within organizations. Passion is defined as a strong and positive feeling toward a specific activity or task, accompanied by a strong desire to participate and personally invest in that activity (Vallerand et al., 2023). Recent studies have highlighted the importance of passion as a key element in enhancing job commitment, developing employee performance, and creating a positive and healthy work environment (Forest et al., 2022). According to the dualistic model of passion, passion is divided into two main types: harmonious passion and obsessive passion. Harmonious passion refers to a positive engagement with an activity with flexibility and balance, leading to enhanced personal happiness and productivity at work (Zhang et al., 2025). Obsessive passion expresses intense, almost obsessive, involvement, which can lead to psychological and emotional stress and poor mental health due to difficulty disconnecting from work (Choi et al., 2020). Recent studies have confirmed that consensual passion is positively associated with innovation, job flexibility, and overall career satisfaction (Forest et al., 2022). Employees with consensual passion have also been found to be more adaptable to organizational changes, which enhances overall organizational performance (Vallerand et al., 2023). Conversely, studies have shown that obsessive passion, while capable of driving employees to high levels of performance in the short term, often leads to negative outcomes such as job burnout and poor work-life balance (Choi et al., 2020). Therefore, researchers recommend fostering a work environment that supports consensual passion to mitigate the negative effects

associated with obsessive passion (Zhang et al., 2025). Furthermore, recent studies indicate that organizational leadership support plays a significant role in enhancing employee passion levels. It has been shown that leaders who provide consistent support and clear guidance can effectively stimulate consensual passion, which positively impacts organizational performance and creativity (Madaan et al., 2024). Research has also shown that professional development programs and targeted training can increase employee passion levels, especially when they align with their personal and professional values and aspirations (Imperator, 2017). Obsessive passion also presents additional complexity, with researchers suggesting it can be a positive force if effectively managed through organizational interventions that enhance self-awareness and the ability to manage stress (Amarnani et al., 2020). Furthermore, it has been found that balancing the two types of passion through human resource management strategies can contribute to achieving organizational sustainability and enhancing the quality of work life (Benitez et al., 2023). Passion in the workplace is a positive psychological factor that influences job satisfaction. It represents a driving force that motivates employees to engage in their work with passion and dedication (Benitez et al., 2023). Passion, particularly harmonious passion, refers to an individual's balanced and flexible attachment to their work, contributing to their perception of the meaning and personal value of work. This positively impacts feelings of satisfaction and overall career satisfaction (Vallerand et al., 2023).

One of the most prominent ways passion influences job satisfaction is by enhancing the personal meaning of work. Passion drives employees to view their daily tasks as meaningful activities that enable them to fulfill their personal and professional beliefs, which increases job satisfaction (Forest et al., 2022). Passion also enhances intrinsic motivation, which is one of the most important determinants of job satisfaction, as employees engage in work out of love and belonging, not just for financial rewards. Furthermore, passion contributes to enhancing positive emotions and reducing stress, leading to a more psychologically healthy work environment and reducing job burnout, which is positively associated with job satisfaction (Choi et al., 2020). Passion also supports person-organization fit by enhancing congruence between employee values and organizational culture, an important mediating relationship that explains how passion leads to greater job satisfaction (Madaan et al., 2024).

In addition, passionate individuals typically contribute to a positive social work environment due to their effective interactions with colleagues and high willingness to collaborate, which enhances the quality of work life and employee satisfaction (Zhang et al., 2025). Here, person-organization fit emerges as a mediating variable that can explain how and why passion at work leads to job satisfaction. Person-organization fit reflects the degree of alignment between an employee's values, beliefs, and goals, on the one hand, and the organization's culture and orientations, on the other. This alignment enhances an employee's sense of belonging and acceptance, and creates a psychological and social environment that contributes to motivation, reduces stress, and achieves a balance between self and organization (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005; Kristof-Brown & Schneider, 2023). Studies have shown that employees who feel a fit with their organizations exhibit higher levels of satisfaction, even when the nature of their tasks is stressful or changing, because their perception of value congruence provides them with a sense of meaning and empowerment (Kaur & Kang, 2021). From this perspective, individual-organizational fit is a crucial explanatory mechanism in the relationship between passion and satisfaction. It is the mediator that translates the positive emotions resulting from passion into positive job outcomes, such as satisfaction and commitment. In the absence of this fit, passion can become a source of psychological stress, especially if the individual feels the organization does not reflect their values or appreciate their efforts. Therefore, examining this mediating role represents a qualitative addition to organizational behavior models and helps build a balanced work environment that motivates employees and supports their psychological and professional health.

Based on the above, this study aims to explore the relationship between passion at work and job satisfaction, and to test the mediating role played by individual-organizational fit. The results of this study are expected to contribute to developing a theoretical understanding of the psychological factors influencing satisfaction, in addition to providing practical recommendations for human resource management to enable them to attract passionate employees and enhance their alignment with the organizational culture, thus supporting sustainable performance and employee loyalty.

2. Person-Organization Fit

Person-organization fit is a central concept in the literature of organizational behavior and modern management. It refers to the degree of harmony and compatibility between an individual's personal traits—in terms of values, tendencies, and expectations—and the organizational culture and internal environment. Studies have shown that this fit directly impacts organizational behaviors and employee psychological and functional outcomes (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005; Kristof-Brown & Schneider, 2023).

This concept is viewed as a psychological mechanism that contributes to building a sense of belonging and fostering a positive relationship between the individual and their workplace. When an employee feels that the organization, they work for reflects their core beliefs and meets their professional aspirations, they develop a deep sense of job satisfaction and increased commitment to the organization's goals. This sense of fit is not limited to value-based aspects; it extends to the perception that the organization provides adequate support, necessary resources, and sufficient space for personal development, which enhances the quality of work life and reduces stress and burnout (Cable & DeRue, 2002; Hoffman & Woehr, 2006; Kaur & Kang, 2021).

According to recent studies, the match between employees and their employing institutions greatly contributes to enhanced individual output, innovation, and team cohesion at the workplace. Further, this match helps in understanding how different variables within the organization, like leadership, motivation, and professional enthusiasm, can affect an employee's level of job satisfaction

or whether they intend to quit. Kaur and Kang (2021) found that job satisfaction depended not only upon a supportive leadership style but also related to whether an employee perceived that his/her competencies and skills were well utilized in the organization. The results of similar studies conducted by Park and Hai (2024) implied that emotional and behavioral responses are better when there is value similarity in organizations than not.

Nonetheless, fit is seen as an evolving rather than stable concept; change of one's values or circumstances within an organization may lead to adoption of various management approaches supporting continuous integration and positive interaction between both sides. Similarly, according to Boon et al. (2011), employee empowerment programs that involve giving employees decision-making authority, acknowledging their accomplishments, and actively engaging them in work are some of the key elements of this fit. Individuals develop perceptions about whether they fit into a role or not through continuous interaction with various elements present within an organization, as indicated by Piasentin and Chapman (2006); hence, there is a need to take into account the totality of factors that constitute the work setting itself. The issue of person-job fit has been explored not just within the confines of theoretical speculation but also with a view towards its practical implications on human resource management, such as recruitment, training, development programs, as well as fostering strong corporate cultures (O'Reilly et al., 1991).

Individual-organizational fit is one of the essential psychological pillars that contribute to job satisfaction. It arises from the employee's perception that there is harmony between their values and personal interests and the organization's culture and orientations. This cognitive congruence enhances the employee's sense of belonging and reduces stress and professional alienation, which increases job satisfaction (Kristof-Brown et al., 2005; Cable & DeRue, 2002). When an individual feels that the organization embraces their identity and values their contribution, they experience a state of psychological reassurance and emotional stability, which are essential elements in building sustainable job satisfaction (Hoffman & Woehr, 2006; Kristof-Brown & Schneider, 2023). Fit gains an additional dimension in the context of psychological motivators such as passion at work, as it is a crucial link that explains how positive passion translates into tangible job satisfaction. A passionate employee, despite having a strong intrinsic motivation, does not feel fully satisfied unless they find a work environment that reflects their values and provides an outlet for self-fulfillment. Here, fit plays a mediating role, transforming the emotional energy generated by passion into a state of professional satisfaction through goal congruence, mutual appreciation, and a sense of meaning in daily work (Kaur & Kang, 2021; Madaan et al., 2024).

Research has shown that the relationship between passion at work and job satisfaction is stronger and more stable when the level of fit between the individual and the organization is high, confirming that the mere presence of passion is not sufficient to achieve satisfaction; rather, it requires an appropriate organizational context that resonates with and embraces this intrinsic motivation. Hence, fit is viewed as a necessary regulatory condition for transforming positive emotions into desired job outcomes, making it a strategic tool for directing positive energies toward commitment and performance (Park & Hai, 2024; Boon et al., 2011).

3. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is an important topic in human resource management and organizational behavior, given its direct impact on employee performance and job stability. Job satisfaction is defined as the positive emotional state an individual experiences toward their job, resulting from the employee's perception that their work fulfills their professional and personal needs and aspirations (Judge et al., 2020).

According to recent studies, job satisfaction depends on various factors, both within the organization and personal level, such as the nature of work, support from top management, freedom on the job, and integration of work and family life issues (Aung et al., 2023). The recent studies have also shown that there is a positive relationship between employees' job satisfaction and certain characteristics of a supportive workplace, which is described as one that provides all required resources for work without forgetting to identify at work (Duignan et al., 2024).

Job satisfaction is viewed as a crucial determinant that influences the general performance of the organization, given that contented workers portray elevated levels of organizational citizenship and are less likely to quit their jobs with comparably increased productivity than dissatisfied ones, as stated by (Abdullahi et al., 2024). It has been found out through studies that job satisfaction plays a role in enhancing both the mental and physical conditions of employees; it does so by reducing cases of stress, burnout as well as improving on work life quality (Koroglu & Ozmen, 2022). Conversely, reduced job satisfaction leads to a variety of negative outcomes, including high employee turnover, decreased performance, and increased absence, thereby undermining organizational effectiveness and sustainability (Kessler et al., 2020). Therefore, due to the significance of this concept, job satisfaction should be improved through effective leadership practices that focus on continuous enhancement of the working environment, creation of supportive interaction between superiors and subordinates, and giving prospects for career development (Judge et al., 2020; Aung et al., 2023).

Recent studies have also confirmed that job satisfaction is significantly influenced by organizational justice, as employees feel satisfied when resources are distributed fairly, decision-making is made, and incentives and rewards are provided fairly (Lee & Rhee, 2023). Research has also shown that effective leadership, mentoring, and continuous support from leaders play a significant role in enhancing employee job satisfaction (Dubey et al., 2023). Furthermore, training and professional development contribute significantly to increased job satisfaction, as they help employees improve their professional skills and abilities and enhance their

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sense of competence and self-confidence at work (Sesen & Ertan, 2022). Flexible organizational policies that allow employees to achieve a better work-life balance have also been shown to significantly enhance job satisfaction (Chang, 2024).

Based on the above, the following hypotheses can be proposed.

H1: Passion in the Workplace has a significant and positive relationship with Job Satisfaction.

H2: Passion in the Workplace has a significant and positive relationship with Person-Organization Fit.

H3: Person-Organization Fit has a significant and positive relationship with Job Satisfaction.

H4: Person-Organization Fit mediates the relationship between Passion in the Workplace and Job Satisfaction.

Figure 1. Research model

METHODOLOGY

Data Collection and Sampling

Table 1 presents a detailed demographic analysis of the study sample, which comprised 224 participants working in the government banking sector, who responded to a questionnaire measuring work passion and job satisfaction. The data are distributed according to several key variables: gender, age group, educational level, and years of service, helping to paint an accurate picture of the responding sample. In terms of gender, females constituted the largest proportion of the sample, representing 56% (137 participants), compared to 44% (107 participants). This indicates a clear female dominance in the sample composition, which may be reflected in the results related to passion and satisfaction. Regarding age, the largest proportion of participants was concentrated in the 26–35 age group, representing 31% (76 participants), followed by the 36–45 age group, representing 26% (63 participants). The younger age group (under 25 years) represented 17%, reflecting a good representation of young and professionally active age groups. Older age groups also participated less frequently, with those aged 56–60 representing approximately 9%, which may indicate the study's focus on the middle-class workforce.

Regarding educational level, the results showed that the majority of participants held a bachelor's degree (88% (215 participants), indicating a high educational level of the sample. In contrast, the percentage of diploma holders (6%) and master's and doctoral degrees combined did not exceed 3.5%, indicating that the study results primarily reflect the views of bachelor's degree holders. Regarding years of service, participants' experience varied. Those with 6–15 years of experience ranked first, representing 35% (equivalent to 79 participants), followed by those with 16–25 years of experience, representing 27%. This reflects that the majority of participants have medium to long-term work experience. Those with less than 5 years of experience constituted a small percentage, representing 7.5%, indicating that passion and job satisfaction were measured within the context of a largely mature professional experience.

Overall, these indicators show that the sample represents a segment of employees with a high level of education and medium to long-term experience, who are often concentrated in the active age group, with a significant female representation. This provides a solid basis for more reliable analysis of the relationships between the study variables.

Table 1. shows the characteristics of the participants.

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	107	44%
	Female	137	56%
Age	Below 25 years old	41	17%
	26-35 years old	76	31%
	36-45 years old	63	26%
	46-55 years old	27	11%
	56-60 years old	22	9%

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Education level	diploma	15	6%
	Bachelor's	215	88%
	Higher diploma	2	1%
	Master's	5	2%
	Doctorate	4	1.5%
Years of service	Less than 5 years	18	7.5%
	6-15 Years	20	35%
	16-25 Years	85	27%
	26-35 Years	66	17%
	36-40 Years	41	9%
	More than 40 years	22	4%

MEASURES

Selection of Measures

Three validated measures will be used to assess the primary variables of the current study: work passion, person–organization fit, and job satisfaction. These scales were selected based on their strong psychometric properties and relevance to the theoretical framework of the study.

The work passion level can be gauged through the Harmonious and Obsessive Passion Scale, advanced by Vallerand and his colleagues in the year 2003. It is made up of 14 items that differentiate between harmonious passion and obsessive passion for work. Harmonious passion can be described as a high liking towards the job that does not cause any problems with other areas of one's life; but on the other hand, obsessive passion is seen as an ever-compelling drive for one to be at his or her working station, the fact identified with increased work-home conflicts. "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree" responses in a Likert format with seven points were employed for this scale.

Person-Organization Fit Scale: To assess the level of fit in terms of values between employees and their organizations, a scale of nine items developed by Cable and DeRue (2002) will be used in this study. It explores whether employees see their values as aligning closely with their organization's culture, objectives, or work environment. The respondents give ratings using the 5-point Likert scale. High scores indicate that one is highly compatible with and aligned to the organization, and this has been found to predict positive job attitudes and behaviors. This scale measures job satisfaction through a brief five-item measure that was formulated by Judge, Bono, and Locke (2000). The scale offers a short yet comprehensive measurement of general job satisfaction. These instruments have often been used in research on organizations, where they show good internal consistency and validity.

STATISTICAL RELIABILITY

The calculation of Cronbach's alpha coefficient revealed that there was good consistency within each of the scales employed in the research concerning their items. This means that every item measured the construct consistently.

DATA ANALYSIS

The purpose of the data analysis in the research is to examine how well certain hypothesized relationships conform to some predetermined theoretical framework. First, the study confirms that the indicators are appropriate for measuring latent variables by using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to test the fit of the observed data concerning the posited measurement models. This step intends to ascertain that the included items evaluate the stipulated constructs. Statistical fit indices are then employed to gauge the model's fit, among which the most common ones include: chi-square statistic (χ^2), CFI, TLI, RMSEA, SRMR, and GFI. If these indices fall within an acceptable range, then it can be concluded that the measurement model is sufficient. Once this is done, the next step is to examine the relationships among variables through mediation models predicated on Andrew F. Hayes' work described in the following text, "Introduction to Mediation, Moderation", and Conditional Process Analysis, using SPSS PROCESS for complex statistical analysis technique application.

Table 2. Factor Loadings

Item	Work Passion	Person–Organization Fit	Job Satisfaction
x1	0.6		
x2	0.83		
x3	0.743		
x4	0.689		
x5	0.512		

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x6	0.512		
x7	0.473		
x8	0.796		
x9	0.69		
x10	0.733		
x11	0.458		
x12	0.838		
x13	0.783		
x14	0.535		
x15		0.523	
x16		0.523	
x17		0.572	
x18		0.66	
x19		0.623	
x20		0.566	
x21		0.695	
x22		0.506	
x23		0.567	
x24			0.597
x25			0.632
x26			0.764
x27			0.53
x28			0.656

The factor loadings for harmonious passion items (x1–x6) ranged from 0.512 to 0.830, indicating good consistency. Obsessive passion items (x7–x14) also showed acceptable to high weights (0.458 to 0.838), supporting the distinction between the two types and confirming the scale’s structural validity. The person–organization fit scale (x15–x23) showed consistent factor loadings between 0.506 and 0.695, indicating a reliable measurement of value alignment between employees and the organization. For job satisfaction (x24–x28), loadings ranged from 0.530 to 0.764, reflecting strong internal consistency and measurement quality, confirming the scale’s suitability for advanced analyses such as mediation.

RESULTS

Measurement model assessment

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics and Pearson Correlations

	Mean	Std. Dev.	WP	P-OF	JS
WP	4.32	0.47	1		
P-OF	4.18	0.42	0.701**	1	
JS	4.10	0.36	0.591**	0.613**	1

Table 3 shows the values of strong, statistically significant positive correlations between the study variables. Passion for work shows a strong correlation with individual-organizational fit ($r = 0.701$, $p < 0.01$) and a moderate to strong correlation with job satisfaction ($r = 0.613$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly, individual-organizational fit is positively related to job satisfaction ($r = 0.591$, $p < 0.01$). These values confirm the interconnectedness between intrinsic motivation, organizational fit, and employee satisfaction and support the theoretical framework that posits that fit and passion together enhance job outcomes. Table 4 exhibits the results of the structural model analysis, demonstrating several significant relationships among the study variables. First, Work Passion (WP) had a positive and significant effect on Person–Organization Fit (P-OF) ($\beta = 0.417$, $t = 6.94$, $p < .001$), with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.302 to 0.532. Second, P-OF positively influenced Job Satisfaction (JS) ($\beta = 0.223$, $t = 3.87$, $p < .001$), with a 95% confidence interval between 0.108 and 0.339. Third, the direct effect of WP on JS was also positive and statistically significant ($\beta = 0.285$, $t = 5.11$, $p < .001$), with the confidence interval spanning from 0.174 to 0.396.

Finally, the mediation analysis confirmed that P-OF significantly mediated the relationship between WP and JS, with an indirect effect of ($\beta = 0.093$, $t = 3.95$, $p < .001$), and a 95% confidence interval between 0.046 and 0.153. These results collectively validate both the direct and indirect effects hypothesized in the research model, highlighting the essential role of organizational fit in channeling the influence of personal work passion toward job satisfaction. Table 4: Summary of Mediation Effects and Model Fit Statistics

Table 4. Mediation Analysis Results Using Hayes PROCESS Model 4

Path	Beta	t-value	p-value	LLCI	ULCI
WP → P-OF	0.417	6.94	<.001	0.302	0.532
P-OF → JS	0.223	3.87	<.001	0.108	0.339
WP → JS (Direct effect)	0.285	5.11	<.001	0.174	0.396
WP → JS (Indirect via P-OF)	0.093	3.95	<.001	0.046	0.153

Structural model assessment

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide compelling evidence for the mediating role of Person-Organization Fit (P-OF) in the relationship between Work Passion (WP) and Job Satisfaction (JS). The results indicate that WP positively influences P-OF ($\beta = 0.417$), suggesting that individuals who are passionate about their work are more likely to experience a strong sense of alignment with the values and culture of their organization. In turn, this sense of fit is positively associated with higher levels of job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.223$), reinforcing the theoretical perspective that alignment between employee and organizational values is a key driver of well-being and engagement at work.

Importantly, the indirect effect of WP on JS through P-OF ($a \times b = 0.093$) was statistically significant, providing empirical support for the hypothesis that P-OF functions as a psychological mechanism through which passion translates into satisfaction. Furthermore, the direct effect of WP on JS ($c' = 0.285$) remained significant after controlling for the mediator, indicating a partial mediation rather than full mediation. This implies that while person-organization fit accounts for a substantial portion of the relationship, work passion also exerts a direct influence on satisfaction, likely through intrinsic motivational pathways and affective commitment.

The explained variance (R^2) for P-OF (49.1%) and JS (42.6%) highlights the robust predictive power of the model, especially in the domain of organizational behavior, where such levels of explained variance are often considered substantial.

Taken together, these findings underscore the dual importance of fostering individual work passion and cultivating organizational environments that reinforce value alignment. For institutions aiming to enhance employee satisfaction and retention, strategies that promote both intrinsic motivation and cultural compatibility are essential. This study extends current theoretical understanding by validating a mediating pathway from passion to satisfaction via organizational fit, emphasizing the strategic interaction between personal engagement and contextual alignment in shaping positive workplace outcomes.

PRACTICAL AND THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

This study offers important theoretical contributions by deepening our understanding of how work passion can act as a psychological driver that enhances job satisfaction through the mechanism of person-organization fit. By confirming the partial mediating role of P-OF, the research enriches motivational and organizational behavior theories by illustrating how personal engagement at work translates into positive attitudinal outcomes within the workplace.

From a practical standpoint, the findings emphasize that organizations should not rely solely on hiring passionate individuals. Instead, they must create organizational environments that foster value alignment, inclusion, and supportive cultures in which passion can be sustained and meaningfully channeled. Leaders and HR professionals should recognize that fit development—through onboarding practices, value-based recruitment, and cultural integration—is a complementary process to nurturing passion, and is essential for unlocking its full potential in enhancing employee satisfaction and long-term commitment.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Despite the strength of the model and the significance of the findings, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, this study employed a cross-sectional design, which limits the ability to infer causal relationships between work passion, person-organization fit, and job satisfaction. Longitudinal studies are recommended to capture how these relationships evolve, particularly as employees' passion and perceptions of fit may change with organizational experiences.

Second, the data were collected from a specific sector and cultural context—government-owned banks in one country, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future research could benefit from cross-sector or cross-cultural comparisons to validate the model in diverse organizational settings.

Additionally, this study focused solely on person-organization fit as a mediating variable. Future research could examine alternative or complementary mediators such as psychological safety, organizational support, or employee engagement. It may also be valuable to explore moderating variables, such as leadership style, workload, or organizational climate, to better understand the conditions under which work passion most strongly predicts job satisfaction.

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